

DEMOCRACY RELOADING

GOVERN WITH YOUTH

CHANGE TRACKER

SELF-ASSESSMENT TOOL FOR IDENTIFYING THE IMPACT AND SOCIAL CHANGE OCCURRING AS A RESULT OF YOUTH POLITICAL PARTICIPATION IN MUNICIPAL DECISION MAKING

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PEOPLE, DIALOGUE & CHANGE

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WELCOME TO CHANGE TRACKER!

WHAT is the Change Tracker! assessment tool?

This self-assessment tool aims at identifying successful engagement with decision making within youth political participation activities. It is designed to quickly assess how effective youth political participation activities are at influencing municipal decision making and what changes they create. The tool will help you assess:

- How effectively has your project engaged with decision makers?
- What impact has your project had on decision making? (i.e., what changes to policy have happened)
- How has your project increased young people's involvement in local democracy?

Using this tool will help you develop the Democracy Reloading Key Competency of “**Creating a supportive environment within the municipality to involve young people in decision making**”.

In particular:

- **Understanding** - I understand the political environment of the municipality in relation to youth policy.
- **Skills** - I mobilise and cooperate with other relevant stakeholders at all levels for improving youth participation in decision making.
- **Organisation environment** - The political representatives recognise and support youth participation in decision making.

WHAT should the tool be used to assess?

The tool should be used to assess ONE youth political participation activity you have run **which aims to enable young people to influence municipal decision making**. An activity can be a single event, an ongoing initiative, or a short programme of activities. Before you start you should be clear exactly which activity you are assessing, as well as when this activity started and finished. For example, imagine you are working with a local youth council that has organised a youth event, as well as several other participatory activities. You could use the tool to assess the youth council and all of its activities over the previous year, or just the youth event itself. You can choose whichever option is most useful to you, but it is important to be clear what you are assessing before you start. The quick checklist in Section 1 will help you identify if the tool is suitable for your activity.

WHEN should the tool be completed?

The tool is designed to be completed AFTER you have run an activity. It is a way of looking back, evaluating, and reflecting on your work. Doing this will help you identify possible improvements to future activities. However, you might also find it useful to use the tool when planning a new activity. When using it this way, you will not be able to answer all of the indicators; but, it can still help identify areas for improvement in your activity plan, providing you with an ex ante overview of your plans.

WHO should complete the tool?

The tool is designed for municipality staff or local youth workers running youth participation activities. This tool is designed to be simple and flexible. It can be completed just by project leaders or collectively with a team of project staff/volunteers. Alternatively, the tool can be completed in a participatory process with young people who have been involved in the activity you are assessing. If you are able to, you can also discuss your answers to some of the indicators with policy makers who have been involved in your activity. This will give you a different insight and perspective on your work, and will be a valuable opportunity for learning for all involved stakeholders: young people, policy makers, and the activity team alike.

WHAT can the tool not be used for?

The Change Tracker! tool is only designed to assess the impact and effectiveness of engagement with decision making. When assessing your youth political participation activities there may also be other dimensions to assess, which are not covered by the Change Tracker! tool, such as:

- **Assessment of young people's learning:** Involvement in youth political participation activities can offer learning opportunities to young participants and allows them to develop a range of different opportunities. If you wish to assess this area we recommend tools such as:
 - The European Platform on Learning Mobility's [Quality Framework For Learning Mobility In The Youth Field](#), or
 - The Council of Europe's [Reference Framework Of Competences For Democratic Culture](#).
- **Assessment of the quality and meaningfulness of an activity's work with young people:** Within youth political participation activities young people can be active in various roles, and contribute to different processes and outcomes. It is important that any youth participation activities engage young people in a meaningful way, considering issues like power sharing and inclusion. If you wish to assess the way your project engages and works with young people we recommend:
 - SALTO PI's [Planning For Participation](#) tool, or
 - The European Youth Forum's [Policy Document On Quality Youth Participation And Representation In Institutions](#).
- **Assessment of staff and stakeholder competences in the field of participation:** All involved stakeholders contributing to youth political participation processes bring in some type and level of competences. Having a quality mix in the team is key. If you wish to assess staff and stakeholder competences we recommend:

Reference Framework Of Competences For Engaging Young People In Municipal Decision-Making and also Democracy Reloading Online Toolkit both created by Democracy Reloading Strategic Cooperation of National Agencies for Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps.

HOW should the tool be completed?

To complete the self-assessment follow these steps:

Step 1 - Complete the Youth Political Participation: *Basic Checklist* in Section 1.

The checklist will quickly tell you if the rest of this self-assessment tool is suitable for your particular youth participation activity as there are certain aspects that need to be taken into account when talking about youth political participation activities.

Step 2 - Identify people who will be involved in the self-assessment exercise.

It can be done by yourself, or it can be done by a wider team including young people and policy makers. Everyone involved in completing the self-assessment should take some time to read the tool. This will help familiarise them with what the indicators mean, and what meeting them looks like. This creates grounds for fruitful discussions within your team on impacts of youth political participation in local decision making.

Step 3 - Complete Section 2: “Quality and impact of engagement with decision makers”.

This section of the tool explores the way in which your activity worked with decision makers, and the effect your activity had on policy and decision making. There are 15 indicators within Section 2. To complete the assessment you will need to give your activity a rating for each indicator. There may be some indicators which you do not know the answers to or may be harder to complete accurately unless you have gathered feedback on your activity from policy makers. If necessary, make a plan for how you can gather more evidence to complete this part of the self-assessment. For example, you could consider distributing a short survey to the decision makers involved, or simply contact them directly to ask for feedback on your activity and its impact. Once you have assessed all of the indicators, use the final page of the self-assessment tool to calculate your score. You can now see if your activity is rated Bronze, Silver, or Gold, and in combination with the concrete results from different indicator sections, you also see where in particular the strong suits are, and where you can identify potential for improvement!

Step 4 - Complete Section 3: “Impact on involvement of young in local democracy”.

This section of the tool explores the impact your activity had on young people's involvement with local democracy. It explores the various ways your activity might have increased young people's direct engagement in democracy and democratic decision making. There are 12 indicators within Section 3. To complete the assessment you will need to give your activity a rating for each indicator. Once you have assessed all of the indicators, use the final page of the self-assessment tool to calculate your score. You can now see if your activity is rated Bronze, Silver, or Gold, and in combination with the concrete results from different indicator sections, you also see where in particular the strong suits are, and where you can identify potential for improvement!

SECTION 1. Youth Political Participation: Basic Checklist

This section will help you identify if your youth activity is a **youth political participation activity**. This is important because, in case your activity is another type of participatory process, subsequent steps in this assessment tool might not be applicable to your activity, and the Change Tracker! tool might not be suitable for you.

What does the Youth Political Participation: Basic Checklist tell you?

- It helps you identify youth political participation activities, initiatives, or projects and distinguish these from others.
- It helps you identify weak spots of planned activities, initiatives, or projects in case your aim is political participation.

What does the Youth Political Participation: Basic Checklist NOT tell you?

It does not tell you anything about the quality of your activity, initiative, or projects: Maybe you have a different type of activity (civic participation, perhaps?) which works very well in your context and fulfils all expectations of the young people it serves! Maybe you have an activity that still needs some space and energy to grow! Or maybe you just realised that political participation is not what you want to implement in any case!

Within the field of participation, several terms exist that can sometimes be mixed up together and create confusion, and it is best to clearly define them.

- **Participatory processes** refer to such proceedings that are offering space for engagement to different actors, i.e., enable different actors to actively take part in what is going on at the moment. This can apply to numerous contexts and it is a very wide term; for example: participatory research, participatory workshop, or participatory conference.
- **Civic participation** is a narrower concept which describes such participatory processes that enable citizens to directly take action that increases the well being of communities or a society. Volunteering (i.e., investing one's own time to help implement different initiatives) is a typical example of civic participation. Civic participation aims at activities that directly benefit certain causes through means that are very practical and focus on having direct impacts on the world around us. These types of activities can be seen as direct actions of young people, as is well described in [Youth Participation Strategy For The Erasmus+ And European Solidarity Corps Programmes.](#)

SECTION 1. Youth Political Participation: Basic Checklist

- **Political participation** is narrower still and these are only initiatives that are (a) voluntarily done (b) by citizens (c) in an active manner and (d) aiming at policy domain. The main difference between civic and political participation lies in the aims. While civic participation aims at direct action (e.g., volunteering to support young Roma through youth work activities), political participation aims at policy change (e.g., negotiating with a local government to set up a youth centre where young Roma can meet with their peers and engage in non-formal learning activities). This type of activity can be seen as “voice of young people”, as elaborated in [Youth Participation Strategy For The Erasmus+ And European Solidarity Corps Programmes](#).

ALL IN ALL... ALL IN ALL... ALL IN ALL...

... There are many processes that can be described as participatory, but they do not necessarily have anything to do with civic or political participation!

... There are civic participation processes that aim at direct support of the well being of others, such as volunteering activities!

... There are political participation processes that aim at influencing the policy domain, decision making, and change on a systemic level.

In order for any activity, initiative, or process to be described as youth political participation, it needs to fulfil four key criteria:

- Political participation needs to be voluntary.
- Political participation needs to offer active engagement of young people.
- Political participation needs to be done from the perspective of young citizens.
- Political participation needs to aim at the policy domain.

In order to clearly see if the activity you want to assess is indeed a political participation one, you can use the Youth Participation: Basic Checklist below to see if the activity meets the criteria. The diagram below gives you a full overview of the checklist and there is a blank version in the annexes for you to complete.

(1) For a more detailed debate on defining youth political participation, see EU-CoE Youth partnership research study [Meaningful Youth Political Participation In Europe: Concepts, Patterns And Policy Implications](#).

YOUTH POLITICAL PARTICIPATION: BASIC CHECKLIST

There are four sections in this Checklist, each containing concrete questions.
If you answer YES to all questions in this Checklist,
you can be sure your project can be described as a youth political participation!

Political participation needs to be voluntary.

- Is it the choice of young people to take part?
- Can young people stop participating at any time?
- Are young people free from any pressure to participate?

Political participation needs to be done from the perspective of citizens.

- Is the activity aiming at improving public well being?
- Is the activity primarily done for reasons other than monetary gains or other personal benefits?

Political participation needs to offer active engagement of young people.

- Are young people actively contributing to the process?
- Are young people's contributions to the process used to shape results of the activity?

Political participation needs to aim at the policy domain.

- Are proceedings or results of the activity purposefully designed to influence policy making or decision making at municipal, regional, national, or international level?
- Are proceedings or results of the activity shared with relevant policy makers at relevant levels?

SECTION 2. Quality and impact of engagement with decision makers

This section allows you to rate your activity against **15 indicators relating to decision makers**. The indicators evaluate the **quality and impact of your activity's engagement with decision makers**. If the activity meets all of the relevant indicators fully, **it is more likely to have an impact** on municipal policy making. But keep in mind that impact on policy and decision making can never be guaranteed. Even with the best designed youth participation activity you may not be able to influence policy making. Policy and decision making is also affected by many external factors such as economic issues, or political priorities of municipalities and their elected representatives. The needs and views of young people are just one factor that influences municipal decision making.

To complete this section of the tool, rate your activity against each of the 15 indicators shown in the tables below. The tables describe each of the indicators and what they mean. For each indicator you can score your activity in one of five ways:

- **Fully achieved** - The activity has met this indicator completely.
- **Nearly achieved** - The activity has nearly met all aspects of this indicator.
- **Achieved to a small extent** - The activity has some aspects of this indicator, but there are substantial areas for improvement.
- **Not achieved** - The activity has not met this indicator.
- **Not relevant / Do not know** - This indicator is not relevant to the activity, or the answer is not known.

There is a blank assessment scorecard in the annex for you to record your indicator ratings on. At the end of the assessment you can also use the scorecard to calculate a final score. Ideally, you want your activity to score “fully met” on all of the relevant indicators. This will give you a maximum score and a Gold rating.

GROUP 1 - ENGAGING WITH THE RIGHT DECISION MAKERS

The indicators in this group focus on which decision makers are involved with a youth participation activity. Involving the right decision makers is crucial to ensuring that the activity is able to make impact on policy making

Indicator	Things to think about
<p>1 All of the topics and issues discussed during the activity were directly relevant to the decision makers who were involved.</p>	<p>To meet this indicator, the decision makers involved in the activity should have roles and responsibilities that are relevant to the issues and topics raised by participants. For example, if the topic of the activity is schools, it could involve head teachers, educational decision makers, and local politicians with responsibilities for educational programmes.</p>
<p>2 All of the relevant stakeholders who are responsible for taking decisions on the topics of your activity were engaged during the activity.</p>	<p>A range of different actors are usually involved in policy making. To meet this indicator, the activity should involve all, or most, of the relevant decision makers in the municipality. For example, an activity with the topic of leisure and culture that only includes youth sector decision makers might not meet this indicator. This is because there may be other decision makers, with responsibility for things such as sports, or museums, or libraries, which were not included in the activity.</p>
<p>3 The decision makers who were involved in your activity were senior enough to influence to lead change based on the topics discussed.</p>	<p>To meet this indicator, decision makers involved with the activity need to have responsibilities at a senior level. This means they are more able to take action based on the things that young people say. An activity that engages only decision makers who do not have substantial decision-making power would not meet this indicator.</p>
<p>4 The decision makers were involved in your activity on an ongoing basis.</p>	<p>To meet this indicator, an activity needs to engage with decision makers on a regular basis, rather than through a one-off activity.</p>

GROUP 2 - COMMUNICATING MEANINGFUL MESSAGES AND RECOMMENDATIONS TO DECISION MAKERS

The indicators in this group focus on the messages and recommendations made by young people to decision makers during the activity. They explore how much these messages were useful, valued, and trusted by decision makers. Ensuring that decision makers find the information they receive valuable and useful helps maximise the impact of the activity on policy making

Indicator	Things to think about
<p>5 Decision makers who were involved in your activities believed that the messages and recommendations coming from your activity are trustworthy and reliable sources of information, and (if appropriate) representative of young people's views in general.</p>	<p>To meet this indicator, decision makers need to have trust and confidence in the things that are said by the activity participants. To enable this, they need to have a clear understanding of if participants represent a wide range of young people, or only a specific section of young people. This enables decision makers to take into account if any young people's views are missing from the dialogue.</p>
<p>6 The messages and recommendations coming from your activity provided in-depth, useful information to decision makers on the topics discussed.</p>	<p>To meet this indicator, the recommendations and ideas proposed by young people need to provide enough detail to be useful to decision makers when they are writing policies. For example, an activity that recommends to decision makers that "youth information services need to be improved" is less useful to decision makers than an activity that explains how youth information services can be improved and what the current problems are.</p>
<p>7 The messages and recommendations coming from your activity identified new issues / solutions and or insights that were not previously known to decision makers.</p>	<p>Many decision makers may already have a good understanding of young people's needs and views. To meet this indicator, an activity needs to help decision makers involved in the activity further develop their understanding and knowledge of the activity topics and young people's views on them. An activity that repeats information the decision makers are already aware of may not achieve this.</p>

GROUP 3 - LINKING TO EXISTING DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES

The indicators in this section explore how well the activity links to existing decision-making and policy-making processes within the municipality. Connected to, and finding synergies with, existing processes helps the activity maximise impact on policy making.

	Indicator	Things to think about
8	The activity was well connected to an upcoming policy agenda.	Policy making is usually linked to ongoing programmes of work. For example, a municipality may intend to review its youth policy once every two years. A participation activity will be able to influence policy making if it is directly connected to the current or upcoming activities of decision makers. To meet this indicator an activity needs to be connected to the ongoing policy-making process.
9	Decision makers who were involved in your activity were supportive of the participation of young people in general.	To meet this indicator, decision makers involved in the activity need to be supportive and committed to listening to the views of young people when they make policies.
10	Your activity was connected to existing democratic mechanisms within the municipality.	Policy making within a municipality is influenced by a range of different democratic mechanisms and processes. To meet this indicator, the activity should take account of these mechanisms and consider how the activity might connect to them (e.g., timetable of presenting new proposals to a Municipal Council, respecting rules for such proposals, etc.). If appropriate, time and resources should be included in the activity for engaging with these mechanisms. For example, this could mean supporting activity participants to engage with existing civil or political participation initiatives, such as local council meetings, youth advisory bodies linked to the municipality, etc.

GROUP 4 - IMPACT ON DECISION MAKING

The indicators in this section focus on what changes and actions are taken by decision makers who were involved in your activity, as a result of the recommendations made by activity participants. Policy making is a slow and complex process, so this can include concrete changes to policy, but also commitments to other actions related to the topics of your activity. You will only be able to complete this section after your activity has engaged with decision makers. Even in the most successful activity it is unlikely that all of the indicators in this section will be fully met. In most cases only one or two might be achieved. In many instances achieving one indicator may make the other indicators no longer relevant.

	Indicator	Things to think about
11	A change in policy was made or planned to be made by decision makers who were involved in your activity.	To meet this indicator, decision makers should make a concrete change to policy based on the recommendation made by young people in your activity. Policy making is a slow process, so this can also include a plan to implement a change in the near future.
12	Decision makers involved in your activity made a commitment to advocate to other decision makers for issues raised by participants of your activity.	In some situations the decision makers involved in your activity may not be able to make changes themselves. To meet this indicator, decision makers should give a commitment to raising the issues of recommendation coming from your activity with other decision makers who are able to act on them.
13	Decision makers who were involved in your activity made a commitment to engage further with young people on the topic of your activity.	In some situations decision makers may wish to engage with other groups of young people about the topics of your activity. They might also wish to meet with participants of your activity again. To meet this indicator, the decision makers should give a commitment to doing one of these things.
14	Decision makers who were involved in your activity made a commitment to gather more research and evidence related to the topics of your activity.	In some situations decision makers may need to gather further evidence and research on the topic or recommendations of your activity. To meet this indicator, they should commit to doing this.
15	Decision makers who were involved in your activity gave feedback on what changes and actions are planned based on the results of your activity.	To meet this indicator, decision makers should give feedback to the young people on what policy changes they will make, or what actions they take, based on the recommendations made by participants of your activity. This feedback should occur during or soon after the end of your activity. If decision makers do not intend to make changes, they can also give feedback to the participants of your activity as to why not. Giving feedback is an important part of transparency and accountability in policy making.

SECTION 3. **Impact on involvement of young in local democracy**

Youth political participation on the local level should be meaningfully designed in such a way so that the aims of the activity are in line with the mechanisms the activity intends to use to achieve these goals. In other words, the mechanisms used by your youth political participation activity must be able to achieve its aims. Subsequently, the aims should be reached in order to make the youth political participation an impactful one. This section describes different aims and presents indicators to check impacts of any given youth political participation activity on development of opportunities to involve young people in local democracy. The main focus of the indicators is on systemic impacts towards involvement of young people in local democracy, not on individual developments and learning. This is true even in the case of developmental aims: the indicators in this instance cover creation of learning opportunities within political participation activities, but do not assess their effectiveness to learning of individuals.

There are four distinct types of aims in youth political participation:

Rights-based, Empowerment, Efficiency, and Developmental

(for more, see [Meaningful Youth Political Participation In Europe: Concepts, Patterns And Policy Implications Research Study](#)):

- **Rights-based aims** of youth political participation activities focus on facilitating access to the political participation opportunities for young people. This can be done by utilising existent democratic mechanisms, by adjusting these mechanisms, or by creating completely new ones.
- **Empowerment aims** of youth political participation activities underline young people's role in decision making, and overall stress power-sharing between the local government and young people and their representatives. Apart from traditional democratic mechanisms (i.e., voting and running for office), young people can become part of specific decision-making bodies, lead consultations with young people on various topics, or even initiate official negotiations between the democratic structures and youth representation platforms.
- **Efficiency aims** of youth political participation activities target the domain of policy making by striving for creating such policies that are in line with the needs of young people, and that are implemented in line with young people's preferences and expertise. Various advisory bodies and monitoring think tanks are examples of activities that take up the efficiency aims.
- **Developmental aims** of youth political participation activities enable young people to gain participatory skills through engagement in real-life situations where they learn about various political participation mechanisms through a hands-on approach. Small-scale democratic mechanisms (e.g., school councils, school referenda, etc.) as well as different youth-led organisations and projects are all contributing towards the developmental aims of youth political participation activities.

Now that the types of aims are presented, they can be used to assess your youth political participation activity with respect to its impact on involvement of young people in local democracy. First, identify your concrete aims and determine what types of aims these are. Second, have a look into the infographic below and identify the indicators of the aim types relevant to your activity. As youth political participation activities are very diverse and also can be quite complex, it is possible that your aims will fall under several of the aim types, and in some cases also even under all of them. For each indicator you can score your activity in one of five ways:

- **Fully achieved** - The activity has met this indicator completely.
- **Nearly achieved** - The activity has nearly met all aspects of this indicator.
- **Achieved to a small extent** - The activity has some aspects of this indicator, but there are substantial areas for improvement.
- **Not achieved** - The activity has not met this indicator.
- **Not relevant / Do not know** - This indicator is not relevant to the activity, or the answer is not known.

There is a blank assessment indicator grid in the annex for you to record your indicator ratings on. At the end of the assessment you can also use the scorecard to calculate a final score. This will give you an assessment of Gold, Silver, or Bronze. Ideally, you want your activity to score “Fully achieved” on all of the relevant indicators because that would mean that you fully achieved all of your aims and highly positively impacted involvement of young people in local democracy. This will give you a maximum score and a Gold rating.

What can this assessment tell you about your youth political participation activity?

- Firstly, if you are able to identify at least one indicator that says “Fully achieved”, “Nearly achieved”, “Achieved to a small extent”, or “Not achieved”, then your youth political participation activity is meaningful, because it does aim at relevant targets by relevant means.
- Secondly, if you are able to identify at least one indicator that says “Fully achieved”, “Nearly achieved”, or “Achieved to a small extent”, then your youth political participation activity is impactful, because at least one of your aims was, to some extent, achieved.
- Thirdly, you can further work with those indicators you identified as “Not achieved”. Think on what happened, what can be improved in the future, and how success in these areas can be achieved, what barriers need to be tackled, what obstacles to overcome.
- Fourth, have a look at the indicators you identified as “Not relevant / Do not know” and try elaborating on whether perhaps your youth political participation activity could be adjusted to include these indicators as relevant in the future. That way, you can try widening the scope of your youth political participation activity and potentially widen its impacts.

Impact of Youth Political Participation on Involvement of Young People in Local Democracy

Rights-based

Supporting young people's access to political participation processes

Young people's voting turnout in referenda or elections was increased

Young people's participation in bodies representing youth in state bodies was increased

Young people's engagement in consultations on various topics was increased

Young people's engagement in state-led platforms for policy dialogue was increased

Empowerment

Enabling young people to make changes in the world around them through power sharing and decision making

Young people more frequently initiated referenda or other similar direct democracy mechanisms

Young people more frequently run for an office

Young people's engagement in decision-making bodies was increased

Young people led consultations more frequently

Young people's engagement in youth-led platforms for policy dialogue was increased

Efficiency

Enabling young people to work with municipalities on improving policies

Young people were more frequently involved in referenda or other similar direct democracy mechanisms via engagement in advisory bodies

Young people more frequently supported local government via engagement in advisory bodies

Young people more frequently engaged in advisory bodies designing and/or evaluating policies

Development

Enabling young people to develop their skills by engaging in political participation processes

Young people more frequently engaged in various democracy mechanisms, including those with a limited scope (e.g., a school referendum, neighbourhood council, youth centre advisory body, or a municipal youth consultation process, etc.)

Young people more frequently engaged in youth-led NGOs or youth-led local civic initiatives

ANNEX 1

Youth Political Participation: Basic Checklist

<p>There are four sections in this checklist, each containing concrete questions. If you answer YES to ALL questions in this checklist, you can be sure your project can be described as a youth political participation!</p>		
<p>Political participation needs to be voluntary.</p>	<p>1. Is it the choice of young people to take part?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
	<p>2. Can young people stop participating at any time?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
	<p>3. Are young people free from any pressure to participate?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Political participation needs to offer active engagement of young people.</p>	<p>4. Are young people actively contributing to the process?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
	<p>5. Are young people's contributions to the process used to shape results of the activity?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>

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Youth Political Participation: Basic Checklist

<p>There are four sections in this checklist, each containing concrete questions. If you answer YES to ALL questions in this checklist, you can be sure your project can be described as a youth political participation!</p>		
<p>Political participation needs to be done from the perspective of citizens.</p>	<p>6. Is the activity aiming at improving public well being?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
	<p>7. Is the activity primarily done for reasons other than monetary gains or other personal benefits?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Political participation needs to aim at the policy domain.</p>	<p>8. Are proceedings or results of the activity purposefully designed to influence policy making or decision making on municipal, regional, national, or international level?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
	<p>9. Are proceedings or results of the activity shared with relevant policy makers at relevant levels?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>

ANNEX 2

Engagement with decision makers: Scorecard

Indicator group	Decision-maker Indicators	Assessment
<p>Engaging with the right decision makers</p> <p>(i.e., are the decision makers involved in your activities the ones you need to engage with?)</p>	<p>1. All of the topics and issues discussed during the activity were directly relevant to the decision makers who were involved.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	<p>2. All of the relevant stakeholders who are responsible for taking decisions on the topics of your activity were engaged during the activity.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	<p>3. The decision makers who were involved in your activity were senior enough to influence to lead change based on the topics discussed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	<p>4. The decision makers were involved in your activity on an ongoing basis.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know

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Engagement with decision makers: Scorecard

Indicator group	Decision-maker Indicators	Assessment
<p>Communicating meaningful messages and recommendations to decision makers</p> <p>(i.e., Were the things your participants said useful, valued, and trusted by decision makers?)</p>	<p>5. Decision makers who were involved in your activities believed that the messages and recommendations coming from your activity were trustworthy and reliable sources of information, and (if appropriate) representative of young people’s views in general.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	<p>6. The messages and recommendations coming from your activity provided in-depth, useful information to decision makers on the topics discussed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	<p>7. The messages and recommendations coming from your activity identified new issues / solutions and or insights that were not previously known to decision makers.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know

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Engagement with decision makers: Scorecard

Indicator group	Decision-maker Indicators	Assessment
<p>Linking to existing decision-making processes</p> <p>(i.e., How well did your activity link to policy making within the municipality?)</p>	<p>8. The activity was well connected to an upcoming policy agenda.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	<p>9. Decision makers who were involved in your activity were supportive of the participation of young people in general.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	<p>10. Your activity was connected to existing democratic mechanisms within the municipality.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know

ANNEX 2

Engagement with decision makers: Scorecard

Indicator group	Decision-maker Indicators	Assessment
<p>Impact on decision making</p> <p>(i.e. What difference did your activity make to policy making?)</p>	<p>11. A change in policy was made or planned to be made by decision makers who were involved in your activity.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	<p>12. Decision makers involved in your activity made a commitment to advocate to other decision makers for issues raised by participants of your activity.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	<p>13. Decision makers who were involved in your activity made a commitment to engage further with young people on the topic of your activity.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	<p>14. Decision makers who were involved in your activity made a commitment to gather more research and evidence related to the topics of your activity.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	<p>15. Decision makers who were involved in your activity gave feedback on what change and actions are planned based on the results of your activity.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know

CALCULATING YOUR ACTIVITY'S FINAL SCORE

Use the chart below to calculate your final self-assessment score:

Fully achieved indicators	<i>Write the total number of indicators your activity has fully achieved here:</i>	<i>Multiply the number of fully achieved indicators by 10:</i>
Nearly achieved indicators	<i>Write the total number of indicators your activity has nearly achieved here:</i>	<i>Multiply the number of nearly achieved indicators by 5:</i>
Indicators achieved to a small extent	<i>Write the total number of indicators your activity has achieved to a small extent here:</i>	<i>Multiply the number of indicators achieved to a small extent by 2:</i>
Indicators not achieved	<i>Write the total number of indicators your activity has not achieved here:</i>	<i>Multiply the number of indicators you have not achieved by 0:</i>
	<i>Add the four numbers in the boxes above to find the "total number of indicators used":</i>	<i>Add the four numbers in the boxes above to find your "total points scored":</i>
	<i>Multiply the "total number of indicators used" by 10 to find your "maximum possible score":</i>	<i>Divide the "total points scored" by your "maximum possible score" and multiply by 100. This will give you your final rating as a percentage:</i>

Now see how your activity rated in relation to quality and impact on decision making:

Gold level 75% to 100%	Congratulations! Your activity has meaningfully engaged with policy makers in a very high quality way.
Silver level 50% to 74%	Well done! Your activity is on track to meaningfully engage with policy makers. You still have some areas to improve on but you are making good progress.
Bronze level 0% to 49%	Keep going! You have started to make some progress, but still have some distance left to go.

ANNEX 3

Impact on involvement of young people in local democracy: Scorecard

Categorisation of Aims	Community Youth Impact Indicators	Assessment
Rights-based Aims (i.e., supporting young people's access to political participation processes)	1. Young people's voting turnout in referenda or elections was increased	<input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	2. Young people's participation in bodies representing youth in state bodies was increased	<input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	3. Young people's engagement in consultations on various topics was increased	<input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	4. Young people's engagement in state-led platforms for policy dialogue was increased	<input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know

ANNEX 3

Impact on involvement of young people in local democracy: Scorecard

Categorisation of Aims	Community Youth Impact Indicators	Assessment
<p>Impact on decision making</p> <p>(i.e. What difference did your activity make to policy making?)</p>	<p>5. Young people more frequently initiated referenda or other similar direct democracy mechanisms</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know</p>
	<p>6. Young people more frequently run for an office.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know</p>
	<p>7. Young people's engagement in decision-making bodies was increased</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know</p>
	<p>8. Young people led consultations more frequently</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know</p>
	<p>9. Young people's engagement in youth-led platforms for policy dialogue was increased</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know</p>

ANNEX 3

Impact on involvement of young people in local democracy: Scorecard

Categorisation of Aims	Community Youth Impact Indicators	Assessment
Efficiency Aims (i.e., enabling young people to work with municipalities on improving policies)	10. Young people were more frequently involved in referenda or other similar direct democracy mechanisms via engagement in advisory bodies	<input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	11. Young people more frequently supported local government via engagement in advisory bodies	<input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	12. Young people more frequently engaged in advisory bodies designing and/or evaluating policies	<input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know

ANNEX 3

Impact on involvement of young people in local democracy: Scorecard

Categorisation of Aims	Community Youth Impact Indicators	Assessment
<p>Development Aims</p> <p>(i.e., enabling young people to develop their skills by engaging in political participation processes)</p>	<p>13. Young people more frequently engaged in various democracy mechanisms, including those with a limited scope (e.g., a school referendum, neighbourhood council, youth centre advisory body, or a municipal youth consultation process, etc.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know
	<p>14. Young people more frequently engaged in youth-led NGOs or youth-led local civic initiatives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fully achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved to a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> Not achieved <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant / Do not know

CALCULATING YOUR ACTIVITY'S FINAL SCORE

Use the chart below to calculate your final self-assessment score:

Fully achieved indicators	<i>Write the total number of indicators your activity has fully achieved here:</i>	<i>Multiply the number of fully achieved indicators by 10:</i>
Nearly achieved indicators	<i>Write the total number of indicators your activity has nearly achieved here:</i>	<i>Multiply the number of nearly achieved indicators by 5:</i>
Indicators achieved to a small extent	<i>Write the total number of indicators your activity has achieved to a small extent here:</i>	<i>Multiply the number of indicators achieved to a small extent by 2:</i>
Indicators not achieved	<i>Write the total number of indicators your activity has not achieved here:</i>	<i>Multiply the number of indicators you have not achieved by 0:</i>
	<i>Add the four numbers in the boxes above to find the “total number of indicators used”:</i>	<i>Add the four numbers in the boxes above to find your “total points scored”:</i>
	<i>Multiply the “total number of indicators used” by 10 to find your “maximum possible score”:</i>	<i>Divide the “total points scored” by your “maximum possible score” and multiply by 100. This will give you your final rating as a percentage:</i>

Now see how your activity rated in relation to quality and impact on decision making:

Gold level 75% to 100%	Congratulations! Your activity has brought highly positive impacts in involving young people in local democracy.
Silver level 50% to 74%	Well done! Your activity is on track to bring meaningful impacts to involvement of young people in local democracy. You still have some areas to improve on but you are making good progress.
Bronze level 0% to 49%	Keep going! You have started to make meaningful impacts relating to involving young people in local democracy, but still have some distance left to go.